

ISic0610

Milestone of Aurelius Cotta

Language

Latin

Type

milestone

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2002.06.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Corleone

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Corleone, Museo Civico Pippo
Rizzo

Physical Description

The original block is reconstructed to a height of 1.5 m, but only two substantial fragments are preserved after it was broken up by the farmers who found it. The upper fragment is 32 cm high; the lower 26 cm high.

Dimensions

Height 150 cm

Width 46 cm

Depth 33 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-4: 90 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [C(aius)A]urelius ·
2. [L(uci)f(ilius)] Cottas ·
3. [C]onsol ·
4. □VII

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Caius Aurelius Cotta, consul (set this up). 57 (miles).

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175816

EDR 074316
EDCS 13600220

Bibliography

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